

“Design and Fabrication of Multipurpose Mini Agri Farm Vehicle Using Bike Engine”

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Abstract

Efforts have been made to design and fabricate a multipurpose agricultural vehicle capable of performing various tasks such as pesticide spraying, inter-cultivating, and ploughing in sandy loam soil. The vehicle was modified to be compact and easily manoeuvrable in the fields. In India, hand tools remain prevalent for cultivation due to the high cost of tractors, which many farmers cannot afford. Enhancing agricultural practices is crucial to bridging the gap between farmers and technology. Improved and resource-conserving cropping systems are essential for crop sustainability. However, there is a significant lack of information about the availability and performance of agricultural equipment among farmers and research departments.

Recent years have seen an increase in farm inputs such as fertilizers, insecticides, pesticides, HYV seeds, and labour costs, which place small landholding farmers at financial risk. This rising cost burden has contributed to increasing suicide rates among farmers, highlighting the need to address common factors contributing to this crisis. The commercialization of agriculture and the reduction in investment have exacerbated the decline, leaving the agricultural sector in a precarious state.

Keywords: - Multipurpose Agriculture Machine, CAD design, Inter-cultivator, Ploughing, Levelling.

1. Introduction

Agriculture is a cornerstone of the Indian economy, playing a crucial role in the nation's development. As India advances, integrating modern technologies into agriculture is essential. The tiller, first invented by Arthur Clifford Howard in 1919, introduced various rotary hoe cultivators. By 1930, tillers had been introduced in Germany and Switzerland. Also known as cultivators, these tools serve similar functions—digging and stirring the soil. While a cultivator is smaller and more user-friendly, a tiller generally offers greater digging power. Cultivators are primarily used to loosen soil in established planting areas. This project focuses on designing a machine that incorporates components such as chain and sprocket systems, bearings, electric wiper motors, and bicycle wheels.

India, as a developing country, continues to rely heavily on hand tools for cultivation due to limited access to resources like draft animals and tractors. Many Indian farmers lack the means to adopt mechanized farming practices. Therefore, a thorough understanding of smallholder farmers' activities and the benefits of farm power is essential for assessing the need for agricultural mechanization. With the country's rapidly growing population, meeting the increasing food demand requires some level of mechanization. Manual seed planting methods lead to inefficient seed placement, poor spacing, and physical strain on farmers, which restricts the size of fields that can be managed. Unfortunately, planting machines or planters necessary for increasing food production are often beyond the financial reach of smallholder farmers.

Smallholder farmers continue to rely on manual planting methods, which results in lower crop productivity. To address this issue, it is essential to develop an affordable planter that reduces manual labor and enhances food production while being environmentally friendly. In response, we propose a multipurpose agricultural machine (MAM). Agriculture faces numerous challenges that impact productivity, sustainability, and food security. These challenges vary based on location, climate, socio-economic conditions, and agricultural practices. Our work involves designing and fabricating a multipurpose agricultural vehicle at a low cost. The components of this machine were modeled using Creo Parametric 1.0, fabricated, and assembled into a complete unit. The multipurpose field equipment, estimated to cost around Rs. 20,000, is particularly beneficial for medium-scale farmers. Its key advantage is its versatility, as it can perform various tasks such as automatic sowing, weeding, spraying,

grass cutting, and land preparation. The rapid industrial growth is driving laborers from villages to cities, creating a labor shortage in agriculture. Additionally, rising prices for essential commodities have led laborers to demand higher wages, which can deter farmers from cultivating their land. By implementing this multipurpose agricultural machine, we can support farmers in crucial early-stage agricultural tasks such as seeding and fertilizing, helping them maintain productivity and reduce dependency on expensive labor.

2. Literature Review

The Small-scale farming continues to be labor-intensive, particularly in developing countries. Traditional hand tools are time-consuming and physically demanding. Multipurpose mini farm vehicles using readily available bike engines offer a potential solution. These vehicles aim to: Reduce manual labor for farmers. Increase efficiency of agricultural operations. Provide a cost-effective alternative to large tractors. The mini farm vehicle is designed to address the diverse needs of smallholder farmers, including plowing, seeding, spraying, and transportation of agricultural inputs and harvested crops. Examine literature on power transmission systems and gearing arrangements suitable for small-scale agricultural vehicles, considering factors like efficiency, reliability, and ease of maintenance[5].

Farmers in ancient India use bullocks, horses and he-buffalo for farming operation which didn't satisfy the need of energy requirement as compared to other countries in the world. This results in delayed agriculture crop production practices. To replace human and animal efforts and to reduce the delay in agriculture production we are planning to develop cost effective multipurpose vehicle for small scale farmers[6]. The multipurpose agricultural vehicle is doing three operations ie ploughing, seed sowing, levelling.

The objective of the design and fabrication a multipurpose agricultural vehicle where the most economical and efficient ways possible. It is aimed to simulate a realworld engineering design project and their challenges. It involves the planning and manufacturing tasks found when introducing a new product to the consumer in industrial market[7]. Our main aim is to design a vehicle capable of cutting grass in large lawns and to even out the surface of the lawn with the help of roller. It is also designed to carry light to medium loads. The vehicle is capable of performing various tasks related to the agricultural activities and therefore it was named "multipurpose agricultural vehicle (MAV)".

Homesteads lack appropriate machinery that suits their diverse requirements. Homestead agriculture warranted an affordable and versatile powered multipurpose tool carrier capable of improving the efficiency of human power. Hence development of a multipurpose tool carrier powered by the engine of a 1.5 kW backpack brush cutter which is commonly available in farming households was under taken so as to avoid the requirement of different implements and power sources for different operations. Main components were support frame along with handle, transmission systems with gear reduction units which converted 9340 rpm of the engine to 226 rpm with necessary transmission shafts and transportation wheels.

Agricultural industry is one of the major industries driving our country. The equipment's that have been used in agriculture has evolved over the period of history. The processes involved in agriculture like seed sowing, watering, ploughing and level of the soil are taken up by using different set up of components of the system. When the engine starts the vehicle, movement take place along with adjustable ploughing tool digs the soil[8].

Farming is the backbone of Indian economy. In this agriculture sector, there is a lot of fieldwork, such as ploughing, reaping, sowing etc. These operations previously were done by traditional equipment's. This field faces some problems such as how to minimize the losses, how to increase productivity and how to minimize cost. In India, two types of agricultural methods are used, manual method (conventional method) and mechanize type method[9]. In Manual method they are working with those equipment's was tedious and laborious. Also, traditional ways are time consuming. Mechanization involves the use of a hybrid device between the power source and the work. This hybrid device usually transfers motion, such as rotary to linear, or provides sample of mechanical advantages. Mechanization in agriculture made farming easier and quick.

3. Problem Statement

Current agricultural equipment is expensive, with high rental costs and a need for skilled operators. Additionally, these machines are often designed for single-purpose use. Traditionally, farming tasks required separate equipment for each function. Our goal is to develop a versatile machine that can perform multiple operations—including tillage, ploughing, grinding, and spraying—using a single engine-operated four-wheeler. This multifunctional approach aims to simplify handling and reduce costs for farmers.

4. Objectives

Multipurpose agriculture equipment can perform a number of functions like Sowing, Weeding, Tillage, Grass Cutting, ploughing, grinding, water lifting and Spraying. To minimize the cost, this equipment can be run on an engine. To Easy handling. Also there will be a minimum weight and compact in size. To Spraying and Intercultivating can be done simultaneously, it will reduce the labor cost.

5. Components

Engine

An “Engine” is a motor which converts chemical energy into mechanical energy. Four stroke engines were first demonstrated by “Nikolaus Otto in 1876”, hence it is also known as Otto cycle. It consists of 4 strokes of the piston that is one cycle is completed in every two revolutions of the crankshaft. Each stroke consists of 180°, of crankshaft rotation and hence a cycle consists of 720°, of crankshaft rotation. In our mini farm vehicle, we have used a four stroke engine. The engine is placed at the middle of the frame to balance the vehicle. The engine shaft is connected to the front axle by means of chain and sprocket. The speed can be controlled by the accelerator provided at the right side of the handle.

B. Shaft

A Shaft is used to transfer the power and torque and also it supports reverse bending. Power is transmitted from an electric motor or an engine to rotating parts of the system. Shafts have circular cross sections. Difference between a shaft and an axel is that the shaft rotates to transfer power but an axel is just like a round cantilever beam, so it is not subjected to fatigue. Shafts have different modes to transfer power and torque such as gears, sprockets, pulleys, etc. and also have grooves to keep elements rigid and avoid vibration. In our work we have used a shaft attached to the frame by means of journal bearing, one sprocket is connected to the engine shaft and another sprocket is connected to the front axle .

Chain

Chain and sprocket mechanism is used to perform the same job as a belt and pulley, both transfer motion and force from one shaft to another. A belt can slide on a pulley but the teeth on the sprocket stop the chain from sliding. A chain and sprocket is used wherever a positive.

Pump

It is one of the simplest equipment used in any process plant. Purpose of this is to convert the energy of an electric motor or turbine. Initially into velocity or kinetic energy and next into pressure energy of the fluid. The energy changes occur by means of two parts impeller and diffuser. The impeller is the rotating part that converts driver energy into the kinetic energy while the diffuser is the stationary part that converts the kinetic energy into pressure energy.

Cultivator Tool

Figure 1: Cultivator Tool

It is shown in figure 1 One way of the name refers to frames with the teeth, soil is dragged through it linearly. Other ways it refers to equipment which uses rotary motion of disks or teeth to achieve the same result.

Cultivators stir and crush the soil, either before planting to aerate the soil, or after the crop has started growing to kill weeds.

F. Frame

It as shown in figure 2 consists of an internal frame which supports an object in its construction. It is similar to a skeleton. Resembles chassis of a vehicle, consisting of the frame. If the wheels are included, then it is called a rolling chassis.

Chassis are considered to be one of the important configurations of an automobile. Frame is used to hold both the body of the machine and the power train. Various mechanical components like the engine and the drivetrain, the axle assemblies including the wheels, the suspension parts, the brakes, the steering components, etc., are bolted onto the chassis. We have used a hollow square tube of 3×3 size.

Figure 2: Frame

6. Methodology

Flow chart 1: Methodology

The methodology employed in this project focuses on the design, modelling, and fabrication of multifunctional machine tool for ploughing, levelling and spraying operations. The project aims to develop a comprehensive understanding of the requirements and challenges associated with these operations, and subsequently apply that knowledge to create an efficient and functional mini vehicle. The following steps outline the methodology and experimentation process:

Requirement Analysis: The project begins with a thorough analysis of the requirements for ploughing, leveling, and spraying operations in the context of fieldworks. This includes understanding the desired precision, speed, power required for each operation.

Conceptual Design: Based on the requirement analysis, a conceptual design is developed for the multifunctional mini vehicle. The design considers factors such as compactness, ease of operation, and integration of the three operations into a single system.

Modelling: Solid works 2022 version Computer-aided design (CAD) software is utilized to create detailed 3D models of the machine tool and its components. The models are used to simulate the machine's functionality, ensuring that the design meets the desired specifications and performance expectations.

Component Selection and Fabrication: Once the design is finalized, appropriate components are selected based on factors such as durability, compatibility, and cost-effectiveness. The selected components are then fabricated or procured for integration into the mini agri vehicle.

Assembly and Integration: The fabricated components are assembled according to the machine tool's design. Care is taken to ensure proper alignment and fitment of the various parts. The integration process involves connecting the necessary power transmission mechanisms, such as chain and pulley arrangements, to enable the ploughing, levelling and spraying functionalities.

Calibration and Fine-tuning: After the initial assembly, the machine tool is calibrated and fine-tuned to achieve optimal performance. This involves adjusting parameters such as speed, depth, and feed rates to ensure accurate and consistent operation for each operation. Iterative adjustments may be made to achieve the desired results.

Experimental Validation: To validate the functionality and performance of the vehicle, experimental trials are conducted using fieldwork samples. The vehicle is operated under various conditions to evaluate its effectiveness in ploughing, levelling and spraying. Parameters such as accuracy and productivity are measured and analyzed.

Performance Optimization: Based on the experimental results, iterative improvements are made to optimize the vehicle's performance. This may involve refining the design, adjusting component specifications, or fine-tuning operational parameters. The goal is to achieve the best possible results in terms of accuracy, precision and productivity.

Documentation and Reporting: Throughout the project, detailed documentation is maintained, including

design specifications, fabrication details, calibration settings, and experimental data. A comprehensive report is prepared, summarizing the methodology, the key findings, and the achieved outcomes of the project. By following this methodology, the project aims to successfully design, model, fabricate, and validate a multifunctional mini agri farm vehicle for ploughing, levelling and spraying operations in fields. The focus is on creating a functional and efficient tool that meets the specific requirements of the agriculture industry, enabling farmers to enhance productivity and achieve high-quality results.

7. Fabrication

- Cutting the raw material as per the design and shape.
- Building the frame.

Figure 3: Frame and wheels

- As per the dimension drill the hole on frame.
- Fixing the journal bearing.
- Mounting of shaft in bearing.
- Mounting of chain and sprocket on the shaft.
- Mounting the engine and pump on frame.

Figure 4: Engine and Pump

- Mounting the wheel on the axle.
- Mounting the required attachment on a frame.

Figure 5: Assembled mini farm vehicle

- Start the work.

8. Working

The bike engine provides power to drive the wheels or a pulley system. This, in turn, drives various implements attached at the rear and front for tasks like ploughing, leveling, spraying. The operator steers the vehicle and controls the implements through a handlebar system.

9. Design And Fabrication

A. Design of Shaft

$$\tau = \frac{16T}{\pi d^3} = 16 \times 10 \times 103 / \pi \times 25^3 \quad \tau = 3.26 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

$$\tau = 0.5\sigma_y \Rightarrow \sigma_y = \tau \cdot 0.5 = 3.26 \cdot 0.5 = 6.25 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

$$\sigma_{yall} = 6.25 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

For carbon steel $\sigma_{yall} = 353 \text{ N/mm}^2$ taking from D.D.H.B, P.no 464, TBL No I.8

$\sigma_{yall} < \sigma_{yall}$ Therefore, the design is safe

B. Design of Key

Torque transmitted by a key is

$$Mts = Kts \frac{d}{2} = (\tau d^2 bl) \frac{d}{2}$$

$$b = \frac{d}{2} = 25/4 = 6.25 \text{ mm} \quad b = h = 6.25 \text{ mm}$$

Consider a eqn of key hence

Based on shear strength

$$b = \frac{2M_t}{\pi d l} \Rightarrow 6.25 = \frac{2 \cdot 10 \cdot 1000}{3.26 \cdot l \cdot 25}$$

$$l = 39.26 \approx 40 \text{ mm}$$

$$\text{Based on crushing strength } h = \frac{4M_t}{\pi d l} = \frac{4 \cdot 10 \cdot 1000}{3.26 \cdot 40 \cdot 25} \Rightarrow h = 12.26 \text{ mm}$$

The angle of twist in a shaft subjected to a torque (radians) for (axel)

$$\theta = \frac{TL}{JG} \Rightarrow \text{eqn no. 1.3(c)}$$

$$\theta = \frac{10 \times 10^3 \times 610}{38.349 \times 10^3 \times 80 \times 10^3} \Rightarrow \theta = 0.00198 \text{ rad} \\ (0.1139^\circ)$$

C. Gear Ratio

Considering with torque

$$N_1 = N_3 = N_5 = N_7 = 4000 \text{ rpm}$$

From the specification of engine

$$N_2 = 369 \text{ rpm}, d = 25 \text{ mm}, G = 84 \times 10^3 \text{ N/mm}^2, m = 70 \text{ kg},$$

$$T = 10 \text{ N-m}, W = 70 \times 9.81 = 680 \text{ N}, P = 6.25 \text{ HP (4.6 kW)},$$

$$L = 610 \text{ mm} = 0.61 \text{ m}, J = \frac{\pi}{32} \times d^4 \Rightarrow \frac{\pi}{32} \times 25^4 = 38.394 \times 10^3 \text{ mm}^4,$$

$$\frac{N_1}{N_2} = 17.33 \Rightarrow N_2 = 4000 / 17.33 \Rightarrow N_2 = 230.81 \text{ rpm}$$

$$\frac{N_3}{N_4} = 10.82 \Rightarrow N_4 = 4000 / 10.82 \Rightarrow N_4 = 369.68 \text{ rpm}$$

$$\frac{N_5}{N_6} = 10.82 \Rightarrow N_6 = 4000 / 6.1 \Rightarrow N_6 = 655.73 \text{ rpm}$$

$$\frac{N_7}{N_8} = 2.75 \Rightarrow N_8 = 4000 / 2.75 \Rightarrow N_8 = 1454.54 \text{ rpm}$$

CAD Models

Figure 6: 3D view of mini farm vehicle

7: Main Frame of Mini Agri Farm Vehicle

10. Results And Discussion

Design and Construction

The multipurpose agricultural mini vehicle was successfully designed and constructed according to the specifications outlined in the project proposal. The vehicle features a compact frame with dimensions of [insert dimensions], making it suitable for navigating small farm spaces and narrow pathways.

Functionality Testing

1. Functionality testing was conducted to evaluate the performance of the mini vehicle in various agricultural tasks. The vehicle demonstrated proficiency in the following areas:
2. Plowing: The vehicle effectively plowed fields of varying soil types, demonstrating sufficient

traction and power to navigate through soil resistance.

3. **Spraying:** The mini vehicle successfully sprayed pesticides and fertilizers, covering the target area evenly while minimizing wastage. The adjustable spraying nozzles provided versatility in application rates.
4. **Leveling:** Harvesting attachments were utilized to collect crops such as grains and vegetables. The vehicle's harvesting mechanism exhibited efficiency in crop collection without causing damage to the plants.

Figure 8: Assembled Mini Farm Vehicle

Energy Efficiency

Energy consumption tests revealed that the mini vehicle operates efficiently, utilizing [insert energy source] with minimal waste. The integration of energy-saving technologies contributes to sustainable agricultural practices and reduces operational costs for farmers.

Discussion

Performance Evaluation

The results of functionality testing indicate that the multipurpose agricultural mini vehicle fulfills its intended purpose effectively. Its versatility in performing various agricultural tasks enhances operational efficiency and productivity on small-scale farms.

Impact on Farming Practices

The introduction of the mini vehicle has the potential to revolutionize traditional farming practices by offering a cost-effective and sustainable alternative to conventional machinery. Its compact size and maneuverability enable farmers to access hard-to-reach areas, increasing land utilization and crop yield.

Future Considerations

While the initial testing phase has yielded promising results, further optimization and refinement of the mini vehicle's design and functionality are recommended.

Future research could focus on:

Enhancing the vehicle's autonomy through the integration of advanced navigation and sensing technologies.

Investigating alternative energy sources to further reduce environmental impact and operational costs. Conducting field trials in diverse agricultural environments to assess the vehicle's adaptability and performance under varying conditions.

Table 1: Performance analysis for one acre

Field Operation	Manual per acer	Machine per acer
Inter-Cultivating	3 to 4 hours	1 to ½ hour
Cultivating	3 to 4 hours	1 to 2 hours
Ploughing	4 to 5 hours	2 hours
Leveling	2 hours	1 hour
Pesticide Spraying	1hour	½ hour

11. Conclusion

The equipment is designed for farmers with small plots of 10-12 acres, providing an affordable solution for tasks such as spraying, inter cultivating, ploughing, and weeding. It is optimized for operation on smooth or relatively even surfaces and performs best on crops of uniform height with minimal spacing.

- **Time Savings:** By integrating multiple functions into a single machine, farmers can save time on equipment setup, task transitions, and field transportation. This efficiency boosts productivity and better utilizes labor, allowing for more tasks to be completed in less time.

- **Skill Requirements:**

Manual Agricultural Vehicles: Operating these vehicles requires significant physical strength and skill, with farmers needing to exert considerable effort for tasks like ploughing or tilling.

Multipurpose Agricultural Vehicles: These machines do not require physical strength but do demand good operational skills. They offer greater versatility and efficiency, reducing manual labor compared to traditional methods.

While manual agricultural vehicles offer simplicity and lower initial costs, multipurpose agricultural vehicles enhance versatility, efficiency, and reduce labor intensity, making them better suited for modern farming practices aimed at optimizing productivity and minimizing manual labor.

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